

Validation of SCF Formulas for Joint Misalignments in Fatigue Design Rules of the Coast Guard and Navy

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Abstract. This study presents new SCF solutions for axially misaligned butt welds between two plates, derived using the “ASME B&PV Code” mesh-insensitive structural stress method. Two-dimensional finite element models are analyzed across varying boundary conditions and geometries. A direct analytical approach is also taken and results in closed-form solutions corresponding to various plate thickness and length combinations. Additionally, the solutions are validated by those derived using the energy method by Xing and Dong (2018). Results prove that current International Institute of Welding (IIW) formulas, along with other industry standards, contain empirical terms that lack physical basis, have limited applicability to realistic boundary conditions, and generally produce un-conservative estimates of stress concentrations—leading to over-prediction of fatigue life by up to seven times for some misalignment conditions. The demonstrated inaccuracy of IIW formulas for simple misalignments, where analytical solutions are feasible, raises concern for more complex joints. The SCF solutions presented in this study are more accurate and broadly applicable for misaligned butt and cruciform fillet welds on naval vessels, enable identification of the critical weld toe for targeted structural health monitoring, and can be extended to more complex joints. The methods and solutions presented are also used to analyze the impact of tapered transitions in welds of varying thickness.

Keywords: stress concentration factor, misalignment, taper

1 Introduction

Fatigue design of welded joints has been studied for decades, yet premature fatigue failures continue to plague naval vessels, including recent U.S. Coast Guard and Navy acquisitions. Notably, the initial National Security Cutter design for the Coast Guard lacked sufficient structural fatigue considerations, leading to extensive structural enhancement work on the first two hulls and significant redesign for subsequent hulls. To begin addressing these issues, the Coast Guard launched the Fatigue Life Assessment Program (FLAP) [1] to evaluate fatigue design procedures, particularly those outlined in the Navy’s Fatigue Design Guidance for Surface Ships [2].

Industry standards, including the Navy’s guide, outline three primary methods to calculate fatigue life: nominal stress, hot spot stress, and the effective notch stress [2], [3], [4], [5]. Each method defines a stress to calculate, applies a resulting stress concentration factor for a welded connection not explicitly modeled, and classifies the joint into an appropriate SN curve. The nominal stress method, despite its simplicity and widespread acceptance, is challenging in application. Nominal stress is often ill-defined in complex structures and the categorization of joints is ambiguous as joint type, geometry, and loading mode may not perfectly align with existing curves. The hot spot stress and effective notch stress methods employ more detailed finite element models and require fewer SN curve categories. However, these methods have been shown to be sensitive to element type and size [6]. The International Institute of Welding (IIW) guidance even states a “high level of expertise is required on the part of the FEA analyst [5].” While the Navy recognizes all three methods, the nominal stress approach is required unless specific experimental criteria and approvals have been met [2].

Embedded within the fatigue design process is a significant amount of uncertainty. FLAP predominately focused on the wave loading and structural response aspects, which are critical inputs for determining the stress expected in a welded joint over the lifetime of the design. Wave sensors and strain gauges were installed at critical design locations on active cutters to assess the accuracy of current methodologies. In addition, FLAP also highlighted other critical areas of uncertainty in the fatigue design process, such as construction imperfections [1].

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Misalignments are common imperfections in shipyard welds that reduce fatigue life by inducing a secondary bending moment. Some representative axial misalignments are shown in Figure 1, where t represents thickness, and e is the misalignment caused by the offset of the centerlines of two adjoining plates. The impact of the induced secondary bending moment is assessed through a stress concentration factor, k_m , shown in the general form in equation (1). The membrane stress, σ_m , refers to the uniform through-thickness stress, and the bending stress, σ_b is the linearly varying stress gradient. For the geometry of a butt joint, this equation can be rearranged into equation (2), where λ is a factor provided in industry standards. Depending on the reference, some k_m equations only consider the secondary bending moment effects ($\frac{\sigma_b}{\sigma_m}$), rather than the total effect represented by equation (1). For clarity and direct comparison, equations in that form that are discussed in this paper have been adjusted.

$$k_m = \frac{\sigma_m + \sigma_b}{\sigma_m} \quad (1)$$

$$k_m = 1 + \lambda \frac{e}{t} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. Misalignment in a (a) butt weld [7] (b) butt weld with plates of varying thickness, and (c) fillet weld[7]

Industry's trend toward lightweighting and structural optimization has increased the prevalence of misalignments, resulting from welding-induced distortions [8], making it imperative to critically assess associated design guidance. Higher strength, thinner plates are more susceptible to distortion, and require joints with thickness transitions, which inherently have misalignments. The Navy recently drafted a newer version of their Fatigue Design Guidance for Surface Ships, citing major structural failures across three different classes of ships and issuing a warning about the lightweighting trend [2],[8]. Despite this warning, the updated draft fails to provide any additional discussion on misalignments, and still simply suggests finite element analysis or the American Bureau of Shipping's (ABS) 1996 reference with equation (2), where $\lambda = 1.5$.

External design firms contracted by the Coast Guard have not been required to strictly adhere to Navy design standards, and have been permitted to identify and apply comparable industry standards. When shipyard misalignments were discovered in the production of a recent Coast Guard acquisition, IIW guidance was followed [10], which provides additional details compared to the Navy guidance. IIW stress concentration factor formulas for axially misaligned butt welds are presented in equations (3) and (4), with their application explained in Table 1.

$$k_m = 1 + \lambda \frac{e \cdot l_1}{t(l_1 + l_2)} \quad (3)$$

$$k_m = 1 + \frac{6e}{t_1} \cdot \frac{t_1^n}{t_1^n + t_2^n} \quad (4)$$

In IIW guidance, the SN curves are titled by the fatigue assessment (FAT) category that the joint is classified by. Each FAT curve already assumes a certain amount of k_m as an acceptable misalignment. This value is 1.30 for butt joints, when using the nominal stress method and its associated FAT curve, and only 1.05 for the hot spot and effective notch stress methods. Therefore, equations (3) and (4) only need to be applied when a misalignment exceeds what is assumed in the FAT curve. When this is the case, an effective k_m should be calculated using equation (5). Additionally, IIW states that a minimum $k_{m, effective}$, dependent on joint type, must always be applied to numerically determined k_m values that did not explicitly include a misalignment in the model. Taras et al [6] concluded this to be essential, and that current industry standards lacks clarity and sufficient guidance.

Table 1. IIW Misalignment Guidance

Type of Misalignment	Equation	Notes
<p>Axial misalignment between flat plates</p>	(3)	λ is dependent on restraint $\lambda = 6$ for unrestrained joints For remotely loaded joints assume $l_1 = l_2$
<p>Axial misalignment between flat plates of differing thickness</p>	(4)	$t_2 \geq t_1$ Relates to remotely loaded unrestrained joints. The use of $n=1.5$ is supported by tests.

$$k_{m, effective} = \frac{k_{m, calculated \text{ from equations}}}{k_{m, assumed \text{ in FAT curve}}} \quad (5)$$

Many studies have questioned the validity of k_m equations, yet industry standards remain rooted in formulations by Berge and Myhre from the 1970s [11], that were subsequently experimentally validated under specific loading conditions [12]. In 1999, Cui et al [13] used plate theory to investigate equation (2), noting λ to vary amongst literature, and concluding λ to depend on geometry and loading. The study specifically proved the ABS version of equation (2) with $\lambda = 1.5$, still referenced by the new draft of the Navy fatigue guidance, has no justification. In 2004, a Ship Structures Committee report [14], found existing guidance to be too general, and boundary conditions to be an important factor that needs to be addressed. With industry standards largely remaining unchanged following these early conclusions, more recent studies have reignited the issue and questioned the existing approaches. Taras et al [6] assessed the numerical methods against the nominal stress approach for several construction imperfections. Xing et al [15] and Zhou et al [12] presented new analytical solutions for misalignments in welded joints, validated with FEA and experimental data. Mancini [16] developed thin plate solutions with experimental validation, and Rautiainen [17] assessed numerical methods for use on complex joints. Amongst these studies, the following issues have been raised regarding fatigue design guidance for misaligned welds:

1. Limited Applicability - Boundary conditions have been found to significantly impact k_m , yet IIW contains vague classifications, such as “fully restrained”, “un-restrained”, and “remotely loaded”, without clear guidance for adjusting for alternate conditions [9]-[12].
2. Empirical Limitations – IIW formulations are rooted in empirical formulations that lack physical meaning and were derived under specific conditions. Studies have proven formulations to be wrong in certain cases [15], and question the use of $n=1.5$ for different thickness combinations, that is “supported by tests.”
3. Inconsistent Results – The three-industry accepted fatigue design methods produce different stress results, direct users to different FAT curves, and ultimately lead to different fatigue life estimates. Even within each method, ambiguous guidance, subjective joint categorization, and mesh sensitivity yield varying results [6], [12], [14], [15], [17].
4. Non-conservative – IIW approaches have been found to underestimate stress in many cases, leading to overestimated fatigue life, which is especially concerning considering the issues above and the multitude of other factors of uncertainty involved. [6], [12], [15], [16], [17]
5. Lack of critical weld location information in a joint – current k_m formulations do not identify the critical toe, which is critical for structural health monitoring efforts, such as those initiated by FLAP, and effective design. There is lack of clarity on how a taper at a butt joint between two different thickness plates reduces k_m , as IIW simply credits tapered transitions with an alternate FAT categorization.

Of note, Lotsberg [18] asks similar questions, but concludes IIW formulas for axially misaligned butt welds to be sufficient. However, the study was conducted under specific geometry and loading. This paper utilizes the “ASME B&PV Code” mesh-insensitive structural stress method, referred here as the nodal force method (NFM) for two-dimensional analyses, to address these five issues. The NFM is used to analyze joints with various boundary conditions and geometries. Direct analytical solutions will also be obtained when possible, including specific forms derivable from those presented in [12], [15]. These solutions will be used for not only validating the relevant IIW formulas, but also shed light on the regime of validity and corresponding boundary conditions. The NFM is used to assess the effects of weld presence in misaligned joints, which has been ignored in analytically derived closed-formed solutions, in addition to examining the validity of the empirical $n=1.5$ term and studying tapered transitions in welded joints of varying thickness.

2 SCF Analysis

To represent the range of boundary conditions possible for a welded joint on a naval vessel, several cases were studied, listed in Table 2. Cases 0 and 1 are statically determinate cases. Cases 1 through 3 match those studied by Xing [15], enabling validation of the direct analytical approach offered in this study with Xing’s energy method solutions. When comparing against IIW guidance from Table 1, it is assumed that IIW’s “unrestrained” and “fully restrained” are most like cases 1 and 2, respectively. Models for butt welded joints were developed based on Figure 1 (a) and (b) using thicknesses and misalignments provided in [10], with $l_1 = 10t_{max}$. To study the impact of weld placement, l_2 varied. All FEA results were calculated using plane stress elements in ABAQUS.

Table 2. Boundary Condition Cases

Case	Left Boundary Condition	Right Boundary Condition
0	Edge fixed with no rotation	Free
1	Pinned in x and y	Pinned in y
2	Edge fixed with no rotation	Pinned in y with no rotation
3	Edge fixed with no rotation	Pinned in y

2.1 Nodal Force Method in ASME B&PV Code

The “ASME B&PV Code” mesh-insensitive structural stress method presented in [19], addresses the ambiguities associated with stress identification and SN curve categorization in current industry standard fatigue design methods. This robust approach, adopted by ASME in 2007, is explained comprehensively in [20]. Due to the simple geometry of the misalignments in this study, the 2D structural stress definition, the NFM, is utilized.

Unlike the hot spot stress method, which relies on a linear extrapolation of surface stresses to weld toe, the NFM imposes equilibrium equations by using the nodal forces acting on either side of the hypothetical crack plane to yield mesh in-sensitive results, that correlate well with experimental data [12], [15], [19], [20]. Depicted in Figure 2, a free-body cut at the weld toe exposes elements (shaded in blue) and their nodal forces (NFORC in ABAQUS). A summation of these nodal forces in the x-direction, F_{xi} , and nodal moments yields the internal force, N, and moment, M, as written in equations (6) and (7), where $i=1, n$ and n is the number of nodes exposed by the cut. For the example of three through-thickness elements, there is a total of six exposed F_{xi} to sum: one each at the top and bottom nodes, and two at each internal node. Mesh convergence tests conducted throughout the study confirmed the mesh-insensitivity of this method.

Figure 2. An example of the 2D NFM, with three through-thickness elements. There is a total of six F_{xi} to be summed along the red line, representing a free-body cut at the hypothetical crack line at the weld toe [21].

$$N = \sigma_m t = \sum_{i=1}^n F_{xi} \quad (6)$$

$$M = \sigma_b \frac{t^2}{6} = \sum_{i=1}^n F_{xi} \left(y_i - \frac{t}{2} \right) \quad (7)$$

Additionally, this method enables calculation of an equivalent structural stress range parameter, using equation (8). The traction structural stress range, $\Delta\sigma_s$, is the sum of the ranges of bending and membrane stresses, m is 3.6, and $I(r)^{\frac{1}{m}}$ in Eq. (9) is a dimensionless life integral by using a two-stage growth model [22]. Using these definitions, a Master SN Curve is developed, that consolidates various SN curves into a single, unified curve, shown in Figure 3. This approach removes the subjectivity associated with FAT categories, offering consistent and reliable results across different weld types and joint configurations.

$$\Delta S_s = \frac{\Delta\sigma_s}{t^{2m} I(r)^{\frac{1}{m}}} \quad (8)$$

$$I(r)^{\frac{1}{m}} = 0.0011r^6 + 0.0767r^5 - 0.0988r^4 + 0.0946r^3 + 0.0221r^2 + 0.014r + 1.2223 \quad (9)$$

Figure 3. Master SN Curve with scatter bands representing 2 and 3 standard deviations from mean.

2.2 Analytical SCF Solutions

Direct analytical solutions were derived to validate the NFM results. Figure 4 represents the four cases that were listed in Table 2, and their resulting moment distributions. The moment equation is listed for the left side of the model, when treating the applied force, P , as a moment, M , applied at the weld, as in equation 10. For the statically indeterminate cases, cases 2 and 3, the reaction forces and moments were solved for by imposing compatibility conditions in addition to the equations of static equilibrium.

$$M = P \cdot e \quad (10)$$

Formulations for the stress concentrations at each toe, $(k_m)_i$, are provided in Tables 3 and 4, where an i value of 1 or 2 represents the corresponding toe. These were developed using equation (1) and by setting $x = l_i$ in the respective moment equations. Solutions are presented alongside IIW and modified versions of Xing's[15], that enable direct comparison. Xing's original expressions had an alternative numbering format, only considered the secondary bending effect, and used the membrane stress of the right plate, rather than the respective side. While Xing did not directly solve for Case 0, his approach yields identical results to the direct analytical solution. For

case 1, Xing had a typo, where he incorrectly listed t_1 in the numerator instead of t_i . Once corrected, the analytical solutions for case 1 are also equivalent. Comparison of the solutions for the statically indeterminate cases is more difficult due to the introduction of higher order terms. Simplification of formulations for same thickness cases proves equivalency of the direct analytical method and Xing's energy method, and evaluation of results with model geometry offers additional validation of the two methods. Therefore, Table 4 and subsequent discussion of analytical solutions references are singular.

Case 0:

Case 1:

Case 2:

Case 3:

Figure 4. Representative model and direct analytical moment distribution for cases 0 through 3, when treating the misalignment and applied axial force as a moment applied at the center

Table 3. Solution Comparison – Statically Determinate Cases

	Case 0	Case 1
IIW	$k_m = 1 + 6 \frac{e}{t} \frac{l_1}{(l_1+l_2)}$ or, with differing thickness: $k_m = 1 + 6 \frac{e}{t_1} \frac{t_1^n}{t_1^n+t_2^n}$ where $n=1.5$	
Direct Analytical	$(k_m)_1 = 1 + 6 \frac{e}{t_1}$ $(k_m)_2 = 1$ Critical Toe = left toe	$(k_m)_i = 1 + 6 \frac{e \cdot l_i}{t_i(l_1 + l_2)}$ Critical Toe = Larger $\frac{l}{t}$
Xing	$(k_m)_1 = 1 + 6 \frac{e}{t_1}$ $(k_m)_2 = 1$	$(k_m)_i = 1 + 6 \frac{e \cdot l_i}{t_i (l_1 + l_2)}$

Table 4. Solution Comparison – Statically Indeterminate Cases

Case	Case 2	Case 3
IIW	$k_m = 1 + 3 \frac{e}{t} \frac{l_1}{(l_1+l_2)}$ or, with differing thickness: $k_m = 1 + 3 \frac{e}{t_1} \frac{t_1^n}{t_1^n+t_2^n}$ where $n=1.5$	
Analytical [15]	$(k_m)_i = 1 + \frac{6et_i^2 l_1 l_2 (4 \frac{l_i^3 t_1^3 t_2^3}{t_i^3} + 3 \frac{l_i l_1 l_2 t_1^3 t_2^3}{t_i^3} + \frac{l_1^3 l_2^3 t_i^3}{l_i^3})}{l_i (l_2^4 t_1^6 + 4 l_2^3 l_1 t_1^3 t_2^3 + 6 l_2^2 l_1^2 t_1^3 t_2^3 + 4 l_1^3 l_2 t_1^3 t_2^3 + l_2^4 t_1^6)}$	$(k_m)_1 = 1 + \frac{3e(2l_2^3 t_1^4 + 3l_2 l_1^2 t_2^4 + 2l_1^3 t_2^4)}{(l_2^3 t_1^4 + 3l_1 l_2^2 t_2^4 + 3l_2 l_1^2 t_2^4 + l_1^3 t_1^4) t_1}$ $(k_m)_2 = 1 + \frac{9et_2^3 l_1 (2l_2 + l_1) l_2}{(l_2^3 t_1^4 + 3l_1 l_2^2 t_2^4 + 3l_2 l_1^2 t_2^4 + l_1^3 t_1^4)}$

2.3 Comparison

Results from the statically determinate cases, cases 0 and 1, provide important insights into the IIW formulations. Figures 5 and 6 compare FEA results against the analytical solution and current IIW equations for varying misalignment, $\frac{e}{t_{min}}$, and varying weld position, $\frac{l_1}{l_1+l_2}$. These results indicate:

1. Validation of analytical solution with NFM.
2. Boundary conditions have a significant impact. Ignoring their effect and blindly applying IIW formulas can underpredict k_m . Case 0 gets significantly underpredicted by the IIW formulation where $\lambda=6$, and there is no clear guidance on how to treat this specific boundary conditions. For the worst case analyzed, where $l_1 = 0.25l_{tot}$, the IIW life prediction is 7 times the FEA and analytical life prediction.
3. Statically determinate cases do not need the thickness correction term. The inclusion of this empirically derived thickness term, in the IIW formulas, results in an unconservative prediction of k_m for both statically determinate cases. This indicates limited testing conditions in the formulation of the $n=1.5$ term. Despite IIW formula being derived like case 1, for weld positioning where $l_1 < l_2$, the IIW equation seems incorrect. The term should be $\frac{l_i}{l_1+l_2}$, instead of $\frac{l_1}{l_1+l_2}$. Figure 6 shows that the IIW formulation only considers toe 1. When toe 2 is the critical toe, IIW is unconservative. For the worst case analyzed, a case 1 joint with $l_1 = 0.25l_{tot}$, the IIW life prediction is 4 times the FEA and analytical life prediction.
4. Weld positioning impacts k_m . IIW contains no guidance on the proper use of the “remotely loaded” assumption. The “remotely loaded” is unconservative any time $l_1 \neq l_2$.

Figure 5. K_m for varying misalignment, $\frac{e}{t_{min}}$, based on IIW versus analytical and FEA solutions for statically determinate cases. FEA results validate analytical solutions and show underprediction by IIW.

Figure 6. Stress concentration factors for varying weld position $\frac{l_1}{l_1+l_2}$ based on IIW formula, IIW “remote loading” assumption, versus derived solutions and FEA results for statically determinate cases.

Figures 7 and 8 include results from all 4 cases and compare IIW and analytical solutions against NFM results. IIW does not have a solution for case 0. Cases 2 and 3 are assumed to be the “fully restrained” IIW condition. The results from these additional cases indicate:

1. Good correlation between NFM and analytical solution for all cases.
2. Good correlation of IIW equation only for the same thickness case 1 condition. IIW underpredicted critical toe for all other scenarios tested.
3. The IIW empirical different thickness term also underpredicts statically indeterminate cases, and is not validated by other prediction methods. Further investigation into this term is provided in section 3.
4. The non-conservative nature of IIW formulations is exacerbated by a combination of errors in geometries with different thickness combinations and $l_1 < l_2$. Case 3 yielded IIW life predictions 4.3 times the predictions from other methods.

Figure 7. Stress concentration factors at each weld toe for statically determinate cases with different thickness combination of $t_1 = 5mm, t_2 = 9mm$ for (a) same length and (b) $l_1 = 0.5l_2$

Figure 8. Stress concentration factors at each weld toe for statically indeterminate cases with different thickness combination of $t_1 = 5mm, t_2 = 9mm$ for (a) same length and (b) $l_1 = 0.5l_2$

2.4 Cruciform Joints

A cruciform joint with four fillet welds, shown in Figure 9, was tested with the boundary conditions of cases 0 through 3 applied to the ends of the horizontal members. Results for thickness and length combinations matching those studied on the butt welds, produced identical results to Figures 7 and 8, indicating the analytical solutions and NFM method are valid for fillet weld cruciform joints, as well.

Figure 9. Model of cruciform joint with fillet welds.

3 Discussions

The origin of the empirical different thickness term, $\frac{t_1^n}{t_1^n+t_2^n}$ given in Eq. (4) is discussed by Maddox [23]. It was originally hypothesized that this term, with $n=3$, should be included in the k_m formulation, stemming from a ratio of the different moment of inertias in a joint with varying thickness. Maddox thought $n=1.5$ would be more appropriate and conducted experiments on machined and welded specimen similar to those shown in Figure 9.

Figure 10. Drawing of Maddox's machined and machined tapered test specimen [23]

Some interpretation of Maddox's data was necessary, as not much detail was provided on the separation of strain gauge data into axial and bending stress components. A mesh convergence test was conducted on an FEA model to compare surface stress values with the experimental data. It appears Maddox's "remote axial stress," measured at position B (to avoid any potential notch stress effect at position B) in Figure 10, was from the strain gauge reading at the top surface of the specimen, which contains some bending stress caused by the misalignment induced moment and should not be used as a reference stress for determining k_m . It can be shown that the measured values at position A only contains through thickness membrane (σ_m) and bending (σ_b) by using the following expressions [24]:

$$\sigma_m = \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t \sigma_x(y) dy \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma_b = \frac{6}{t^2} \int_0^t \sigma_x(y) \cdot y \cdot dy \quad (12)$$

Analyzing Maddox's data with the above equations shows that no nonlinear notch stress is contained in measurements at position A. Then, for the test specimens and measurement results, the following relationship between his "local axial" stress (or in the terms of this paper, membrane stress), $\sigma_{A-membrane}$, and "local bending" stress, $\sigma_{A-Bending}$, and the top surface stress, σ_{A-Top} exists:

$$\sigma_{A-Top} = \sigma_{A-Bending} + \sigma_{A-Membrane} \quad (13)$$

meaning his definition of stress concentration is:

$$k_{m-Maddox} = 1 + \frac{\sigma_{A-bending}}{\sigma_{B-top}} \quad (14)$$

When comparing equation (14) to the definition of k_m provided in equation (1), Maddox's stress concentrations are artificially low; the denominators are too high for including some bending stress. Therefore, by combining equations (1) and (13), Maddox's experimental values can be corrected using equation (15), allowing direct comparison with the results of this study.

$$k_{m-Maddox-Corrected} = \frac{\sigma_{A-Bending} + \sigma_{A-Membrane}}{\sigma_{applied} \times \left(\frac{t_2}{t_1}\right)} \quad (15)$$

3.1 Validation of FEA with Data

This updated definition of Maddox's experimental k_m from equation (15) exactly matches the ASME guidance on experimentally measuring structural stress [21]. Membrane and bending stresses can be calculated from strain gauge data using equations (16) and (17), where the subscripts "top" and "bottom" refer to the corresponding surface where a strain gauge is located. Mesh-converged FEA models produced in this study can be used to simulate experimental strain gauge measurements. For the FEA simulated measurement method (SMM), σ_{A-top} and $\sigma_{A-bottom}$ are averaged stress values along a 5 mm length of the model, centered at location A, representing the length of strain gauges used in Maddox's experiment.

$$\sigma_{membrane} = \frac{\sigma_{a-top} + \sigma_{a-bottom}}{2} \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_{bending} = \frac{\sigma_{a-top} - \sigma_{a-bottom}}{2} \quad (17)$$

Figure 11 depicts the geometry and nomenclature of the FEA models. Welds were not explicitly modelled, as toe 2 in the tapered model is not a critical location. Therefore, position 1 represents the critical location for both the taper and no taper specimen, and is the location primarily analyzed.

Figure 11. Model geometry and nomenclature. Models did not contain weld; critical location is position 1.

The adjusted experimental values from Maddox, using equation (15) are plotted in Figure 12(a) with FEA data points using the SMM at Maddox's strain gauge location. Results indicate:

1. Validation of SMM results with experimental data.
2. Good correlation of the $n=1.5$ value with FEA models of Maddox's tapered test specimen.
3. It is important to emphasize the $n=1.5$ correlation includes the impact of the taper and specific boundary conditions, that are most like case 2. Maddox had limited test specimen, and for $\frac{t_2}{t_1} = 2.5$, only tested specimen with a taper.

Following the validation of the ASME methods with the experimental data, NFM was conducted on additional tapered models to supplement the limited test data. Results for thickness combinations similar to Maddox's specimen are shown in Figure 12(b). The NFM was assessed exactly at the critical location (Position 1 in Figure 11), since this method is unconstrained by the limitations of strain gauge placement and stress singularity – yielding a more accurate representation of the stress concentration. These results are compared against the k_m values predicted by the analytical solution and by IIW with $n=1.5$ and show good correlation between IIW formula with $n=1.5$ for Maddox's tapered specimen.

Due to the large t_2 of Maddox's test specimen, and the divergence of the tapered NFM results from the IIW prediction at larger eccentricities, additional geometry combinations were modelled and evaluated. Figure 12 contains NFM data points of tapered and un-tapered models for $t_1=5$ mm, and $t_2=8, 9.5,$ and 11 mm. Figure 12(a) represents results for $L_1 = L_2$, and Figure 12(b) represents $L_1 = 0.5L_2$. These results show:

1. The validity and general applicability of the analytical solution for predicting k_m of an un-tapered joint.
2. The minor reduction of k_m due to tapering.
3. The limited applicability of the empirically derived IIW formulation with $n=1.5$ for different geometry combinations. All additional geometries analyzed indicate non-conservative IIW predictions of k_m and fatigue life.

Figure 12. Stress concentration factors comparing (a) FEA at strain gauge location with the experimental data from Maddox, corrected using equation (15), and (b) NFM at Position 1 for tapered model against experimental tapered data.

Figure 13. Position 1 stress concentration factors from FEA for taper and no taper geometries of alternate thickness combinations with $t_1=5\text{mm}$ and (a) $l_1=l_2$ and (b) $l_1=0.5l_2$

3.2 Taper Effect

Based on the experimental data in [23], Maddox also concluded that a taper has no impact on reducing k_m . Therefore, IIW k_m formulas do not explicitly include any taper effects. However, IIW does credit a tapered joint with a FAT categorization change, which is discussed later. The additional insights on Maddox's test specimen and alternate geometries offered by the NFM in this study have indicated a taper does offer a small (but non-zero) reduction of k_m for certain boundary conditions. For Maddox's test specimen, Figure 12 shows this small impact was included in his $n=1.5$ term. Tapered results for the gripped boundary conditions have indicated up to a 6.5% reduction in k_m . Additional analyses were conducted with NFM to further assess the impact of the taper. The moment distributions and bending stresses along the entire length of the model for all four boundary condition cases, with and without tapers, were produced by conducting NFM at the hypothetical cut locations shown in Figure 14. Tapers on the statically determinate cases had no impact. Results from the statically indeterminate cases are shown in Figures 15 and 16. Without NFM, these graphs could not be produced.

Figure 14. Hypothetical cut locations (dashed lines) of NFM for determining moment and bending stress distributions.

Figure 15. Moment distribution for cases 2 and 3, with $t_1=5\text{mm}$ and $t_2=9.5\text{mm}$. Position 1 is located at distance $x=0$.

Figure 16. Bending stress distribution for cases 2 and 3, with $t_1=5\text{mm}$ and $t_2=9.5\text{mm}$. Position 1 is located at distance $x=0$.

Results show very little impact of the taper for case 3, and the most impact from case 2, with a 7% reduction in maximum bending moment and 6.4% reduction in maximum bending stress for a 1:5 taper. A 1:10 taper provides additional reduction, but is infeasible for manufacturing. Further study on the indeterminate cases was done with additional geometry combinations, and tapers. Figure 17 shows the critical position maximum bending moments for various thickness combinations, normalized by the corresponding no taper model. Tapers with slopes of 1:3, 1:5, and 1:10 are represented along the x-axis. Results prove similar for the additional geometry combinations, with a less than 9% reduction in maximum bending moment for a 1:5 taper for Case 2, and less than 2.5% reduction for Case 3.

Figure 17. Position 1 normalized bending moment for different thickness geometry combinations for varying taper.

3.3 Life Prediction

When evaluating the various k_m estimation methods, it is critical to also examine the resulting fatigue life estimates. Due to the exponential relationship between stress and life, seen as log-log linear in SN curves, small variations in k_m can lead to substantial differences in predicted fatigue life. The Master SN Curve, described in Section 2.1, was utilized for comparison with IIW FAT approach with k_m stipulated in Table 1.

Figure 18 compares FEA results with the FAT categorization of tapered thickness transitions. Two thickness transition combinations are shown. First, the structural stress for tapers 1:2, 1:3, and 1:5 is normalized by the membrane stress of the un-tapered model in the top two plots. In the bottom two plots, is a comparison of fatigue lives, normalized against the 1:2 tapered results, to assess the reduction on FAT categorization with increased taper. For the FEA results, fatigue lives were predicted and normalized with the Master SN Curve. FEA fatigue lives were calculated and normalized using the associated FAT curves. Results indicate the FAT categorization associated with tapered thickness transitions significantly overestimates the impact of a taper in reducing the k_m . IIW credits a 1:5 taper with 2.05 times the fatigue life of a 1:2 tapered joint, while FEA results indicate only an increase of 1.1 times.

Figure 18. Taper impact – normalized structural stress and life comparison with IIW.

Fatigue lives were estimated by the ASME and IIW approaches for a model with $t_1=5\text{mm}$ and $t_2=9.5\text{mm}$ with varying tapers under case 2 boundary conditions. Results are shown in Figure 19. The IIW lives were estimated using equation (4) and the associated weld categorization. As mentioned earlier, there is significant ambiguity in

the weld category approach. Unlimited geometries, boundary conditions, and loading combinations makes all-inclusive guidance infeasible, leaving classification subject to interpretation and experience. This is highlighted when searching guidance for butt joints with transitions in thickness only, and not width. It was determined for this scenario, FAT 90 should be used for no taper and 1:2 taper, FAT 80 for a 1:3 taper, and FAT 71 for a 1:5 taper. The boundary conditions associated with case 2 would most likely be interpreted as “fixed boundary conditions.” Therefore, IIW values were calculated using equation (4) with an adjusted λ representing fixed boundaries. Additionally, equation (5) was applied to account for misalignments already represented by the FAT category. The ASME lives were estimated using the NFM and Master SN Curve. For the Master SN curve values, the mean-2s line was used to correspond with the built-in conservatism of the FAT categorization. Results indicate significant over-estimation of fatigue life by IIW FAT curves, crediting a 1:5 taper with a roughly two times increase in life, despite Maddox’s conclusions and the NFM stating otherwise. Based on these results, and studies that have proven SN categories ambiguous and lacking data driven correlation [7], tapers should not be credited with a change in category. The taper is already technically accounted for in the flawed $n=1.5$ term. For the most explicit and exact treatment of the taper, the NFM should be used.

Of note, for additional industry comparison, ABS results would be slightly less than IIW. ABS has no discussion on boundary conditions, and would therefore predict a slightly lower life than IIW. For categorization, all geometries would be considered ABS Class E, regardless of the taper, making ABS more appropriate for taper categorization for this weld. However, for a butt weld that is welded from both sides, with tapers of 1:4 or greater, ABS does credit the taper with a change to Class C. This would increase the life prediction by 2.5 times, significantly overestimating the impact of the taper.

Figure 19. Life comparison of ASME Master SN curve versus IIW FAT categorization of tapered geometry.

4 Conclusions

The NFM and analytical formulations analyzed in this study for k_m of misaligned welded joints offer solutions to the critical issues in current methodology, including: incorrect formulas, mesh-sensitivity, and inability to correlate results amongst various approaches. The solutions provide more insight into welded joints of varying boundary conditions and geometries, including tapered transitions, and can identify the critical toe. The analytical solutions offer replacements to current IIW formulations. Industry standards for welded joints on naval vessels should consider adopting “ASME B&PV Code” methods for FEA to reduce the ambiguity in stress calculation and SN curve categorization.

FEA results, validated by experimental data from [23] indicate tapered transitions in thickness have limited impact on reducing stress concentration in a weld of varying thickness. While a taper is still necessary for ease in

manufacturing, it should not be given so much FAT categorization “credit” for reducing stress concentration. IIW currently significantly overestimates the reduction of k_m due to tapering transitions of thickness in butt welds.

Future extensions of this work include further analysis of the taper to produce closed form solutions. Validation will be done with available published experimental data, such as from a paper by Tariq et al, presented at the 2025 IIW Annual Assembly. This methodology will also be extended to more complex joints and ultimately attempt to develop more robust fatigue design procedures for the Coast Guard and Navy.

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